

Big Data Schooling

Dr. Sacha Noukhovitch, Executive Director and Editor-in-Chief,
STEM Fellowship - STEM Fellowship Journal ,Canada. stemfellowship.org -
journal.stemfellowship.org

INTRODUCTION:

The data-native generation is the first cohort of students that gets more knowledge from electronic sources, than in the classroom. They do more independent, student-driven learning than teacher-guided schooling in class or online.

AIM:

No wonder, the traditional subject-specific and instruction-based learning does not fit data-native generation learning styles that they have honed through the years of using various information technology, the Internet, and even gaming.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Following the years of monitoring and analysis of high school student digital learning practices, it was possible to identify the following main elements of their data-based learning style:

1. Tapping into data and accumulating information by association
2. Crowdsourcing data interpretations and knowledge references
3. Prioritising sources of information, online experts and knowledge based on references and ranking
4. Accelerated thinking and learning in the knowledge networks communities that provide unique opportunity of non-verbal into- and trans- generational exchange a subject matter information and concepts.
5. Active participation in the knowledge networks through contribution and interpretation of relevant information.

RESULTS:

New learning practice creates a foundation for a different pedagogical approach where laws of nature and civics could be learned through the prism of data analysis. This approach, naturally removed the artificial boundaries between learning subjects and changes the whole concept of schooling.

CONCLUSIONS:

New mostly virtual places of learning would be like interest groups that will replace classes and courses. There would not be time restrictions like class or course and no learning process

interrupts except for the ones that participants make themselves. It will be continuous and on-demand learning.

New learning places will ensure cross pollination of ideas and knowledge by combining learners of all ages together. There are not going to be fixed roles and participants would be able to assume instructor and pupil role depending on the topic exercising true reciprocal peer mentorship.

New learning would bring in different data-based learning resources. They could look like topic specific mosaics of Internet resources - composition of electronic scholarly publications, relevant research data and related social network footprint

KEYWORDS:

Digital learners, pedagogy, big data inquiry